

Studies on the Urea-Humic Acid Complex and Its Behaviour towards Cu(II) Ions

S. K. BANERJEE, S. C. DAS and B. DAS

Faculty of Agriculture, University of Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal.

Manuscript received 22 January 1974 accepted 6 December 1975

The interaction of urea with humus acids has been studied. It is found that specially the carboxyl acidity is greatly reduced by this interaction. With increasing concentration of urea, the milliequivalent of sodium hydroxide required to raise the pH's of humic and fulvic acids to a particular value decreases. Cu^{2+} ions added to the urea-humic acid complexes remain mostly in the free state. The phenolic OH and possibly some other groupings are involved in the chelation process only to a limited extent.

UREA is known to form additive compounds with humus substances^{1,4} and with increasing urea concentration the interaction with humus substances also increases within a certain limit. Pal and Banerjee² postulate that urea forms an additive compound with humic acid and COOH of phenolic OH groups present in humic acid are responsible for the formation of additive compound. Ghosh *et al*³ from the ESR study showed that the free radicals present in humic acid play a significant role in the urea-humic acid interaction.

It is known that transitional metal ions form stable complexes with humic and fulvic acids through carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups⁵⁻⁸. Urea, through its interaction with these groupings, is likely to affect the normal chelation processes and consequently the fate of the transitional metal ions, when these are added to the humus substances in presence of urea, must be known. The present investigation deals with the study of the urea-humic acid complex and the behaviour of humic acid in presence of Cu^{2+} ion with different doses of urea.

Experimental

Humus was extracted from a peat soil by a mixture of a solution of NaOH and $\text{Na}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ (pH 13). It was fractionated to humic and fulvic acids and subsequently purified by the method described earlier⁹. A measured quantity of the dialysed humic and fulvic acids with different doses of urea was taken in test tubes and incubated for 3, 10 and 15 days at room temperature. Then the material in each tube was studied electrometrically.

In a separate set of experiment, a fixed amount of humic acid was taken in different tubes and different doses of urea was added and incubated for 10 days at room temperature. After that a fixed quantity (1 ml) of CuSO_4 solution (0.1M) was added to each tube and incubated for another 15 days at room temperature. Then the material in each tube was centrifuged and the

residue after washing and centrifugate were separately titrated electrometrically by caustic soda solution (0.1 N).

Results and Discussion

Figures 1 and 2 show the curves of humic and fulvic acids with different doses of urea. The total acidity of humic and fulvic acids is due to the presence of mainly the COOH and phenolic OH groups^{9,10}. It is observed that the milliequivalent of sodium hydroxide required to raise the pH's of humic and fulvic acids to a particular value decreases with increasing concentration of urea. From the figure it is also observed that specially the carboxyl acidity is greatly reduced by this interaction. This is particularly observed from the conductometric

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of 1) Humic Acid, 2) H. A. + 0.02 gms. urea, 3) H. A. + 0.04 gms. urea, 4) H. A. + 0.6 gms. urea.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titration curves of 1) Fulvic Acid, 2) Fulvic Acid+0.4 c.c. (2%) urea, 3) Fulvic Acid +0.6 cc (2%) urea.

Fig. 3. Conductometric titration curves of F. A.—urea complex.

1) Fulvic Acid, 2) Fulvic Acid + 0.4 cc. (2%) urea, 3) Fulvic Acid + 0.6 cc. (2%) urea.

titration curves of the urea-fulvic acid complexes (Fig. 3). The conductometric titration curves of fulvic acid shows a pronounced initial drop (minima) in specific conductance and a sharp break is observed at about 50 percent neutralisation. The sharp break corresponds, most likely, the neutralisation of carboxyl groups associated with the aromatic ring^{9,10}. With increasing urea concentration, the specific conductance of urea-fulvic acid complex decreases and less alkali is required to have the minima value. This can be verified by

titrating the complex of urea with methylated and acetylated products of humic and fulvic acids. Our investigation in this aspect is in progress. The results are in agreement with the findings of Ghosh *et al*¹¹, who from infra-red absorption spectra of urea-humic acid complex concluded that the complex formation between urea and humic acid took place through nitrogen of urea and oxygen of the carboxylate ions present in humic acid.

The effect of time is also an important factor in the complex formation. It is observed that after 3 days' incubation with different doses of urea, the titration curve (not shown) of the humic acid does not change so much, the only change observed is the initial increase of pH. It is also noticed that almost complete interaction takes place within 10 days because the titration curve of the material incubated for 15 days coincides with the curve of the material incubated for 10 days. pH of the mixture of humic acid and urea increases from 5.4 to 6.6 as the reaction time is increased from 3 to 10 days at room temperature.

If a transitional metal ion is added to a humus substance, there will be the release of protons from the carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups and obviously there will be an initial drop in pH and more protons will be released if the carboxyl and phenolic hydroxyl groups remain more and more in free state^{6,7,12}. Now, it is clear from the above results that urea forms additive compounds with humic and fulvic acids mainly through oxygen of the carboxylate ions. So, when Cu^{++} ion is added to the complex, the protons will be released mainly from the phenolic hydroxyl groups and the amount will be less. Table 1 shows the pH values of urea-humic acid complexes in presence of Cu^{++} . With increasing urea concentration the pH of the centrifugate

Fig. 4. Potentiometric titration curves of the centrifugates in presence of Cu^{++} .

1) Humic Acid + Cu^{++} , 2) H. A. + Urea (0.02 gm) + Cu^{++} , 3) H. A. + Urea (0.04 gm) + Cu^{++} , 4) H. A. + Urea (0.06 gm) + Cu^{++} .

Fig. A

after the addition of Cu⁺⁺ increases gradually. The pH of the residue also increases with increasing urea concentration. This clearly indicates that with increasing urea concentration, the carboxyl group of humic acid becomes more and more inactivated due to the

decomposition of urea is greatly inhibited in presence of humic acid and even at higher pH, urea-humic acid additive product is a quite stable one. The slight initial rise in pH on prolonged incubation of such systems indicates that one of the NH₂ groups present in urea may remain in free state which undergoes slow hydrolysis liberating ammonia. The entire process may be shown by the Figure A.

TABLE 1—pH's OF THE HUMIC ACID IN PRESENCE OF UREA.

Urea added in gms.	pH of the complex	pH of the centrifugate after addition of Cu ⁺⁺	pH of the residue after addition of Cu ⁺⁺
0	4	3.3	4.6
0.02	5.5	4.0	4.7
0.04	6.1	4.4	5.2
0.06	6.4	4.6	5.8
0.08	6.5	5.0	5.9

additive compound formation, as a result of which the amount of proton released decreases progressively. From the sharp fall of initial pH (Curve 1, Fig. 4), it is clear that—COOH and—OH groups are involved in chelation of Cu⁺⁺. The addition of urea to the humic acid significantly alters the situation. The remaining curves (Fig. 4) indicate that Cu⁺⁺ ions added to the urea-humic acid complexes remains mostly in the free state, as evident from the plateau or buffering region in the curves (this is because of the consumption of alkali by the free metal ion to form metal hydroxide). The phenolic OH and possibly some other groupings (enolic, amino, imino etc.) are involved in the chelation process of copper only to a limited extent. On increasing the period of incubation the situation does not change much. This means that the hydrolytic

References

1. A. E. DRAGUNVA, *Guminovye Udoberniya. Khersonsk. Sel's Kokhoz Inst.*, 1957, 47.
2. P. K. PAL and B. K. BANERJEE, *Technol.*, 1966, 3, 87.
3. P. K. GHOSH, G. P. GUPTA and P. K. PAL, *Technol.*, 1966, 3, 156.
4. K. GHOSH, D. PHIL. Thesis, Calcutta University, 1971.
5. M. V. M. DESAI and A. K. GANGULY, B.A.R.C., 1970, 488.
6. S. O. THOMSON and G. CHESTERS, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1970, 21, No. 2.
7. S. K. BANERJEE and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Soc. Soil. Sci.*, 1972, 20, 13.
8. S. K. BANERJEE and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Soc. Soil. Sci.*, 1972, 20, 91.
9. S. K. BANERJEE and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1971, 34, 171.
10. H. VAN DIJK, *Sci. Proc. Royal Dublin Soc.*, 1960, 1A, 163.
11. S. K. GHOSH, A. K. CHAKRABORTTY and P. K. PAL, *Technol.*, 1967, 4, 71.
12. A. E. MARTELL and M. CALVIN, "Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compound", 1952, Prentice-Hall Inc., New York